

Physicochemical Studies on some Antipyrine Biocomplexes

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Antipyrine(1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolin-5-one) (APY) is an important heterocyclic compound of medicinal values which has three potential donor sites. The present work deals with investigation of some antipyrine biocomplexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^I and Hg^{II} ions.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The complexes are sparingly soluble in ethanol but soluble in DMF. The aqua complexes are stable and the aquo complexes generally do not lose their water molecule on heating at 110–120°. Both the Cl atoms are covalently bonded to the Hg^{II} and Ni^{II} ions but ionically bonded with Cd^{II}. This is also supported by the molar conductance values.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd)		
	M%	N%	Cl%
[Hg ₂ (APY).(H ₂ O).(NO ₃) ₂] (Yellow)	52.90 (52.98)	7.76 (7.40)	—
[Hg(APY).(H ₂ O) (Cl ₂)] (Pale yellow)	43.00 (42.98)	6.20 (6.00)	15.42 (15.20)
[Zn(APY) (H ₂ O) ₃](CH ₃ COO) ₂ (Pale green)	16.13 (15.74)	6.42 (6.73)	—
[Cd(APY).(H ₂ O) ₃]Cl ₂ (Yellow)	27.15 (27.00)	7.03 (6.75)	16.95 (17.10)
[Co (APY).(H ₂ O) ₃](CH ₃ COO) ₂ (Blue)	14.83 (14.56)	7.10 (6.91)	—
[Ni(APY)(PY) ₂ .(H ₂ O)Cl ₂]H ₂ O (Pale green)	12.20 (11.67)	11.02 (11.27)	14.22 (14.28)

The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are diamag-

netic. The Hg^I complex is also diamagnetic due to its dimeric nature. The μ_{eff} values for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are 4.5 and 3.1 B.M. respectively. Experimentally it has been found that the tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes have magnetic moments in the range 4.3–4.7 B.M. while those of the octahedral¹ complexes are 4.7–5.2 B.M. Thus the Co^{II} complex is more likely to be tetrahedral rather than octahedral. The experimental magnetic moment value (3.1 B.M.) for the Ni^{II} complex indicates the presence of two unpaired electrons with octahedral geometry.

Electronic spectra of [Ni(APY)(PY)₂Cl₂(H₂O)]·H₂O exhibit three peaks at 11 000, 20 800 and 38 800 cm⁻¹, assigned to transitions ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g} (F), ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (P) and M → L or L → M (CT) respectively. [Co(APY(H₂O)₃)](CH₃COO)₂ complex shows three peaks at 10 400, 15 000 and 40 300 cm⁻¹, assigned transitions ⁴A_{2g} (F) → ⁴T_{1g} (F), ⁴A_{2g} (F) → ⁴T_{1g} (P) and M → L or L → M (CT) respectively. The position of the first two bands and their high intensity support the tetrahedral² structure for the Co^{II} complex. The complex of

Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^I and Hg^{II} do not display any characteristic band in the visible region

The antipyrine molecule is linked to the central metal ions through carbonyl oxygen. This is suggested on the basis of the fact that $\nu_{C=O}$ band observed at 1710 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the ligand disappears from the spectra³ of the complexes. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band of the ligand (1710 cm^{-1}) shifts around $1610\text{--}1615\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. This red-shifting of the $\nu_{C=O}$ band may be due to coordination of the ligand to the metal ions through carbonyl oxygen. The ligand band at 1590 cm^{-1} ($C=N$) has no change in $C=N$ bond order in complex formation. Hence, coordination has not occurred through nitrogen of pyrazoline ring. The aceto groups are present as free acetate ions, because their band positions are in the region $1570\text{--}1420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for free acetate ion bond⁴. The IR spectral bands show that the two Cl atoms are at *trans*-positions in the Ni^{II} complex and at *cis*-position in the Hg^{II} complex. In the Cd^{II} complex, evidences are in favour of the presence of ionic chlorides⁵. A strong band at 1436 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex also indicates the presence of coordinated pyridine molecules which are at *trans*-position in the octahedral Ni^{II} complex. The presence of coordinated pyridine is also supported by a medium band at 624 cm^{-1} and weak band at 424 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} complex⁶. The ν_{Zn-OH_2} mode of vibration is observed as a weak band at 380 cm^{-1} and the ν_{Cd-OH_2} mode as a very weak band at 320 cm^{-1} which agree with previously reported mode of vibrations assigned for tetrahedral complexes⁷. The $\nu_{C=O}$ bands of the ligand observed at $810\text{--}992\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears in the spectra of the complexes. This also supports coordination of the ligand through $C=O$ oxygen atom to the metal ions. IR evidence is available for nitrate groups acting as bidentate ligand in the Hg^I complex.

The results reveal that the Co^{II} complex is paramagnetic and tetrahedral, the Ni^{II} complex paramagnetic and octahedral, whereas the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^I and Hg^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and tetrahedral.

Experimental

The ligand antipyrine (APY) was prepared by the condensation of ethyl acetoacetate with phenylhydrazine by the reported method⁸.

All the complexes were prepared under similar experimental conditions described here. For the preparation of $[Hg(APY)(H_2O)Cl_2]$, the ligand (0.174 g, 0.001 mol) in ethanol was added dropwise to an ethanolic solution of mercury(II) chloride (0.271 g, 0.001 mol) with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with alcohol, then with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrant. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 521 and 621 spectrophotometers and electronic spectra were recorded with the help on a Hilger and Watts 525 spectrophotometer. Metals were estimated by standard methods and nitrogen by microanalytical method.

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